

Determination of basic constituents and antibacterial potential of leaves, stem and flowers of *Sonchus asper* in Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Sonchus asper is an annual herb in the asteraceae family found all around the globe. *Sonchus asper* can be used as medication because it has significant chemical ingredients that function as antibacterial agents, preventing germs from growing. The current research was conducted in District Bahawalpur in Pakistan's Punjab Province's Cholistan Desert. *Sonchus asper* was harvested and pounded to a fine powder. The methanol extract was next analysed in the lab. The investigation discovered important bioactive elements such as alkaloids, saponins, phenols, tannins, glycosides, flavonoids, carbohydrates, and steroid compounds present in the plant. Antibacterial tests were also done on the extract of *Sonchus asper* against gram negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and a gram-positive bacterium (*Staphylococcus aureus*). The MICs (minimum inhibitory concentrations) in mg/disk for several methanol plant extracts of *Sonchus asper* stem revealed that the extract had no influence on *Klebsiella pneumoniae* growth. Phytochemicals in the plant reduced the growth of the bacterium strains that were examined. *Sonchus asper* chemical ingredients are commonly employed in government (control) laboratories for pharmaceutical manufacture. *Sonchus asper* leaves are a tasty and nutrient-dense leafy vegetable.

Keywords: *Sonchus asper*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

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INTRODUCTION

The majority of plant species are considered folk medicine because they contain key phytochemicals used to make medications (Majeed *et al.*, 2011; Khan *et al.*, 2017a, b). The historical context for the disclosure and use of diverse restorative plants is as old as the historical context for the disclosure and use of food plants (Ibrar, 2002; Umair *et al.*, 2017). Natural therapeutic agents derived from medicinal plants are biologically active molecules with chemical characteristics. Antibacterial and antioxidant activities are present in these bioactive chemicals, which are linked to the treatment of human illnesses (Oyedemi *et al.*, 2010; Khan *et al.*, 2018).

Sonchus asper belongs to the family Asteraceae and is a tetchy-looking spiky, pointy, rough milk sow thistle (Givens, 2015). (Hussain, 2010) conducted a study on the phytochemicals found in the plant *Sonchus asper*. The plant extract was shown to include bioactive components such as alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, phenol, saponins, and tannins. These chemical compounds are useful in wound healing and also have antiseptic effects. The chemical ingredients produced from plants are used to cure diseases such as cough, bronchitis, asthma, and other disorders such as scabies, constipation, diabetes, and cardiovascular ailments. (Shabbir and colleagues, 2011) In the international food sector, a lot of research has been done on the phytochemicals and biological features of *S. asper* (Vilela *et al.*, 2009). After extraction, this plant can also be utilized to reduce oxidative stress, according to (Shabbir *et al.*, 2011).

Flavonoids are potent antibacterial agents, and their chemical structures and uses control their antibacterial properties (Rasouli *et al.*, 2019). Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and cardiovascular illnesses are all treated with phenolic chemicals (Alpinar *et al.*, 2009). Phenolic compounds are very helpful substances that play an important role in health sciences and are directly linked to the consumption of vegetables and fruits (Cheynier, 2012). Along with flavonoids and phenols, the folk medicinal herb also includes alkaloids which play a significant part in the antiviral capabilities of the plant (Paredes *et al.*, 2001).

Alkaloids, terpenoids, phenols, quinones, flavonoids, glycosides, and tannins are all chemical constituents found in various portions of the plant and their plant juices. These chemical constituents also have antibacterial properties (El-Mogy and Alsanius, 2012). The polysaccharides are frequently detected in the filtration of extracts. To check for photosensitivity, the radish root inhibition experiment was used. The antibacterial and phytocidal activity of *S. asper* was highest in experiments. These actions are potent because they can create bioactive flavonoids, saponins, and phenolic chemicals (Sahreem, 2012).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

COLLECTION AND EXTRACTION OF PLANT MATERIAL

Fresh *Sonchus asper* plant components (flowers, stems, and leaves) were randomly collected from several places in the Bahawalpur district of Punjab, Pakistan. The taxonomic identity of the plant *Sonchus asper* was certified by the Islamia University of Bahawalpur's Department of Forestry, Range, and Wildlife Management. Washing and air drying of fresh plant materials (leaves, stems, and fruits) was done and parts were then ground to a fine powder and stored (Nawaz, 2010). The Soxhlet extraction process was used to create crude plant extract. Ground powder was dipped in methanol, the extract was then placed in a beaker and heated at 30-40°C until all of the solvent had evaporated. The dried extract was stored at 4°C in the refrigerator for future phytochemical study (Yadav and Agarwala, 2011).

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENT'S ANALYSIS

Sonchus asper contains saponins, alkaloids, and tannins, as well as carbohydrates, proteins, amino acids, terpenoids, phenols, flavonoids, and glycosides, according to a preliminary phytochemical analysis (Biren-Shah, 2010).

Test for proteins

2 mL Millon's reagent was added to the crude extract. The production of a white-colored precipitate that became red when heated showed the presence of proteins (Yadav and Agarwal, 2011).

Test for glycosides

2 mL filtered hydrolysate was added to 3 mL chloroform and agitated, followed by the removal of the chloroform layer and the addition of a 10% ammonia solution. The development of a pink tint revealed the presence of glycosides (Biren Shah, 2010).

Tannin detection

Two milliliters of aqueous extract were combined with two milliliters of distilled water and a few drops of FeCl₃ solution to identify tannins. The production of a green precipitate showed the presence of tannins (Agarwala and RNS, 2011).

Terpenoid detection

In this process, the crude extract was mixed with 2 mL chloroform and 3 mL concentrated sulphuric acid. To produce a layer, it was carefully applied. The emergence of a reddish-brown tint in the inner face showed the presence of terpenoids (Harborne, 1973).

Flavonoid detection

Some magnesium ribbon portions were mixed in with the crude plant extracts. Concentrated hydrochloric acid was applied drop by drop. After a few minutes, the presence of flavonoids was revealed by a pink scarlet tint (Vasait, 2017).

Phenol detection

To 10 mg extracts, a few drops of ferric chloride solution were added. The production of a bluish-black tint showed the presence of phenol (Harborne, 1973).

Saponin detection

A few drops of ferric chloride solution were added to each of the 10 mg extracts. The presence of phenol was revealed by the formation of a bluish-black colour (Harborne, 1973).

Alkaloid detection

Mayer's and Wagner's reagents were combined with crude extract in 2 mL of 1 percent HCl and heated slowly. The presence of alkaloids was established by the turbid precipitate.

Steroid detection

After mixing the crude extract with 2 mL of chloroform, concentrated H₂SO₄ was added sideways. The presence of steroids was revealed by a red coloring in the lowest layer of chloroform.

DETECTION OF ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Antibacterial analysis was done by adopting agar disc diffusion method as described by Parekh and Chanda, 2007. Nutrient media was prepared using nutrient agar. One single colony of each microorganism (from the nutrient agar stock culture) was transferred into 10 mL sterile nutrient broth using a sterile loop. In a shaking

incubator at 37°C, the broth cultures were cultured for 16–20 hours (Pandey, 2014). After the media had solidified (75–80 mL), it was transferred to new Petri dishes (14 cm diameter) and allowed to solidify. Bacteria were allowed to grow on the plates for 24 hours before the diameter of the inhibitory zone was measured with a caliper for each test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The results of the qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Sonchus asper* indicate that carbohydrates, saponins, alkaloids, flavonoids, proteins, phenols, and tannins are present in the observed plant parts. Glycosides and terpenoids are absent in the leaves of the plant while the stem of the plant does not contain terpenoids (Table 1). Vasanthi (2012) extracted phytochemicals from the leaves, roots, seeds, flowers, and fragrant plants. Alkaloids, saponins, and flavonoids are plant-derived compounds that can still be present in foods today. It was safe to propose the treatment for heart and circulatory disorders.

Table 1. Qualitative phytochemical analysis of stem, leaves and flowers of *Sonchus asper*.

Phytochemicals	Stem	Leaves	Flowers
Carbohydrates	+	+	+
Saponins	+	+	+
Glycosides	+	–	+
Terpenoids	–	–	+
Alkaloids	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+
Protein / amino acid	+	+	+
Phenols/ Tannins	+	+	+

Note: Present, (-) absent

Hussain (2010) looked at the phytochemicals of the *Sonchus asper* plant. The plant extract was shown to include bioactive components such as alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, phenol, saponins, and tannins. Phenols are used to treat bacterial infections, inflammation, and heart problems. The most abundant chemicals in therapeutic plants are phenols (Alpinar *et al.*, 2009).

Saponins have been discovered to be employed in the preparation of medicines. Saponins have been employed in folk cures and ceremonies in diverse ways, according to historical studies (Hosseinzadeh, 2008). The flavonoids in the *Sonchus asper* plant function as an anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agent. In wound healing, *Sonchus asper* act as synthetic medication (Ambasta, 1992).

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Antibacterial tests were performed on the extract of *Sonchus asper* plant parts (leaves, stems, and flowers) against Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and a Gram-positive bacterium (*Staphylococcus aureus*) (Table 2). The expression of the inhibitory zone that was formed by the application of the plant extract against different disease-causing

bacteria was utilized to evaluate the antibacterial potential of the plant *Sonchus asper*. As a result, the current investigation demonstrates that the *Sonchus asper* has the capacity to inhibit bacterial growth.

Table 2: Inhibition zones (in cm) of stem, leaves and flowers of *Sonchus asper* against four bacterial strains.

Bacterial Strain	Stem	Leaves	Flowers
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	1.0	1.2	1.5
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	1.3	1.4	1.2
<i>Klebsiellapneumoniae</i>	0	0.6	0.5
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	1.6	1.4	1.7

The results of the antibacterial assay revealed that the stem has no inhibitory effect against *K. pneumonia*, and shows maximum inhibition (1.6cm) against *P. aeruginosa*. All the observed plant parts show minimum inhibition against *K. pneumonia* and maximum inhibitory effect against *P. aeruginosa*. Maximum inhibition zone (1.7cm) is observed in the flowers against *P. aeruginosa*. Leaves show average inhibitory potential against all bacterial strains used in the study.

In a similar experiment, the antibacterial potential of the plant *Sonchus asper* was assessed utilizing the expression of the inhibitory zone created by the application of the plant extract against several disease-causing bacteria. The results indicated that *Sonchus asper* has the ability to stop germs from growing (Teugwa, 2013).

Sonchus asper methoxide extracts, in contrast to fungus, were more effective in inhibiting bacterial growth. Several scientific research has shown that antimicrobial activities exist even when plants with a phenolic structure are consumed (Baydar, 2006). The extracts' antibacterial efficacy and total phenolic content were also assessed (Prado, 2007), while saponins found in the plants prevent fungal growth (Aboaba, 2001; Mohanta *et al.*, 2017).

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study reveal that the plant extract can be used for a variety of purposes, one of which is the use of medicinal plants in the pharmaceutical area and antibacterial activity. Because this plant has such a diverse spectrum of chemical components, studying it is a novel method to learn new things and develop new therapies. According to the study's findings, the plant has antimicrobial properties. It was found to be inhibitory to both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. This plant's bioactive compounds are used to treat microbial infections, inflammation, and heart disease. These can also be used to treat wounds as a synthetic medicine.

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